

Original Research

The Impacts of Digital Marketing on Brand Awareness: Consumers Perspectives on Sportswear Industry

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Abstract

For “centuries” manufacturers have been using marketing tools to disseminate information to customers regarding their products. The development of internet has forced companies to use digital technologies to interact with customers and tell them about their products. The purpose of this study was to analyse the impact of digital marketing on brand awareness among the customers of sportswear in Dar es Salaam City, Tanzania. This study applied analytic cross-sectional design to analyse quantitative collected from sportswear customers that were selected using simple random technique. The data was gathered using structured questionnaire from 250 sportswear customers in Kigamboni and Kinondoni districts. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and multiple linear regression model. The findings of this study indicate that, five marketing tools namely, content marketing, social media marketing, affiliate marketing, paid advertising marketing and pay-per-click marketing have positive and significant impact on brand awareness. On the contrary, e-mail marketing was found to have non-significant impact on brand awareness. This study has informed customers that searching for information regarding sportswear products is less time consuming and low cost. Moreover, this study informs sportswear manufacturers have to use more paid advertisements marketing since they capture more customers. Based on the findings, this study recommends that sportswear to invest heavy and continue to improve their paid advertising and pay-per-click marketing campaigns and to combine digital marketing and traditional marketing strategies for effective ad wide coverage in order to achieve higher brand awareness. The two-marketing media can create a synergy that is more beneficial than using either medium separately.

Keywords: Brand awareness, digital marketing, sportswear.

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Introduction

The concept of product marketing is not new. For centuries manufacturers and producers of products have been using marketing as a tool to disseminate information to customers regarding products they offer (Diamantopoulos, 2020). Since there are many manufacturers or producers of the products that have similar characteristics and use, then it is important for them to make customers aware of their products names and the distinguishing benefits they offer. According to Mitiku (2021), every manufacturer and producer has the responsibility to differentiate their brand from the competitor's brand. The degree to which customers recognize a product by its name is called brand awareness (Hakala et al., 2012). Brand awareness by customers is crucial for all business since a strong brand image is a valuable asset for any business (Mitiku, 2021).

Abdelhady, Kamal and Samie (2020) assert that brand awareness not only brings the product name in the minds of customers, but also makes the customers to trust the brand. In the current conditions of increasingly ferocious competition due to technological advancement, brand awareness is crucial than ever before. With the advancement in technology, the process of disseminating information has been changed considerably and the traditional marketing tools such as television, radio, posters and billboards are being replaced by the digital technologies using electronic means such as manufacturers and producers (sellers) websites, blogs or online platforms, social media, short messaging services (SMS) (Abdelhady et al., 2020) and multimedia messaging services (MMS) via mobile phones (Ahmed et al., 2019).

In a nutshell, the development of digital technologies has changed the marketing management setting. The application of digital marketing has transformed the relationships between manufactures or producers and consumers and between consumers (Ahmed et al., 2019). Digital marketing uses digital technologies to help manufacturers or producers increase knowledge of customers about their products (Halik et al., 2021) and improve seller-buyer relationships that encourage repeated purchases (Choedon & Lee, 2020). On digital marketing, real-time interaction between marketers of a manufacturing company and customers can enable them to relay directly the superiority and benefits of their product through digital technologies (Choedon & Lee, 2020). Through digital marketing product information can be conveyed anywhere and anytime to customers to create brand awareness.

With availability of many products in the market today, the purchase decisions of the customers are extensively subjected to a higher level of brand awareness. Customers are now increasingly using digital media to look for information of brands and companies. Product and company profile and information on social media networks are assumed to be reliable and credible sources, more dependable and proper than the traditional marketing (Bruhn et al., 2012). So, with the help of the digital media, the customers can effectively engage with a particular brand more than ever before (Ligaraba et al., 2023). Thus, digital marketing has brought consumers perspectives from perceiving themselves as passive players to active interaction with the manufacturer and producers by among others giving their suggestions on how to improve the products and services to make more effective (Samantaray & Pradhan, 2020; Suresh et al., 2018).

The expansion of digital communication technologies in addition to have changed customers behaviour of searching for information (Kannan et al., 2019), have as well facilitated customers with a variety of information in the form of other peoples' reviews and comments on their experience with a particular product (Jafarova & Tolon, 2022). Digital marketing is thought-out to be likely to arouse intention to share brand information. Researches (ElAydi, 2018; Wu & Li, 2018) show that in traditional marketing, customers will share to fewer potential customers the product information they read, saw or hear from newspaper, television or radio compared with digital technologies such as social media. With digital media customer can share experiences with ten thousand potential customers in no time (Chen et al., 2021). Similarly, through digital marketing such as company websites the manufacturer relays product information to larger population at less cost than before (Voramontri & Klieb, 2019).

On the whole, the main advantages of digital media include demassification, interactivity, and synchronicity (Ariel & Avidar, 2015). Thus, digital marketing has revolutionised the way consumers and marketers in manufacturing firms interact to crate brand awareness to potential customers. Brand awareness is important since over time it can develop customer's loyalty to the brand (Sharma et al., 2020). In the current era, brand loyalty is a strategic endeavour that is more important than attracting new customers since it helps manufacturer and producer to circumvent competitors' threats, and increase sales and revenue (Ioană & Stoica, 2014; Siby, 2021). Besides, brand loyalty encourages consumer to suggest a product to potential or other customers and creates many repurchases, causes higher customer retention rates (Saif et al., 2018) and reduces competitors attacks because loyal customers permanently go after their preferred brands and always identify themselves strongly with a particular brand.

In Tanzania, sportswear industry has in recent years been booming and creating more opportunities for investment (Ungruhe & Schmidt, 2020). The sports enthusiasm, which is becoming a trend among the young and young adults, has helped grow the sportswear industry. In the last ten years, the sportswear has increase from less than 20 manufacturers in 2013 to 102 manufacturers in 2023 (Ghozali & Latan, 2015). This has attracted more businesses in the industry and hence stiff competitions. The spread of the sportswear industry extends in addition to urban areas to rural areas. Therefore, to strive to create awareness of customers, sportswear manufacturers are using digital marketing tools. However, the impact of digital marketing on brand awareness has not been established in the sportswear industry. Therefore, the impact of using digital marketing needs to be analysed in sportswear industry. This study has analysed the impact of digital marketing on brand awareness among the customers of sportswear in Dar es Salaam City.

This paper is organized as follows: following the introduction part, a second part is a literature review with theoretical and empirical studies that shed a light on linkage between theory and practice. The third part elaborates the research and methodology. The fourth section provide data analysis and findings of the study as well as discussions and implications of the findings. Finally, this paper concludes with key points, recommendations, future research directions and limitations.

Literature Review

The theoretical underpinning of the study

Stimulus Organism Response Theory

The Stimulus Organism Response Theory (SORT) establishes that an organism mediates the association between the stimulus and response using various mechanisms that are operating in an organism (Mehrabian & Russell, 1974). These mechanisms in actual fact translates stimulus into behavioural change of an organism, which ultimately leads to a response (Wu & Li, 2018). Various studies (Han et al., 2022; Hetharie et al., 2019; Jayadi et al., 2022; Ligaraba et al., 2023; Segson & Tan, 2018; Wu & Li, 2018) have applied stimulus organism response (SOR) model to confirm SORT. The SOR model was applied by Wu and Li (2018) to substantiate if elements around the shopping behaviour (stimulus) would affect customers (organism) cognitive and emotional state, which would ultimately influence a response. The authors translated stimulus (marketing mix) into behavioural change of an organism (change in customer knowledge about a product), which ultimately leads to a response (brand awareness).

In these studies, marketing mix toward shopping behaviour was investigated with the aim to us a SOR model to confirm the theoretical foundation of customer brand awareness and ultimately loyalty. Therefore, using these ideas, this study develops a conceptual framework to explain how digital marketing can impact brand awareness when grounded through the lenses of SORT. As a result, this study applies SORT to comprehend the mechanisms of how digital marketing (stimulus) impacts customers' knowledge and information regarding sports wears of different manufacturers, which in turn influences brand awareness (response).

Empirical Literature Review

Digital marketing tools are principally a two way web internet application that give the chance to the users to create and share their own content (Kamadi et al., 2022). In one way, digital media is used by manufacturers to interact with customers to tell them about their product benefits and superiority from the competitors'. On the other way, digital media is used by customers to share their experiences and perceptions of different products (Edwin, 2023). The first is regarded as business-to-customer relationship and latter customer-to-customer relationship (Sukrat, 2018). The wide application of digital media has provided the opportunity to the customers to talk about their interests along with a range of features of a particular product (Ahmed et al., 2019). Malanda (2020) and Ariyani and Septiani (2022) have identified several types of digital marketing, namely social media marketing, influencer marketing, affiliate marketing, email marketing, content marketing, search engine optimization, paid advertising and pay per click.

Social media marketing has been acknowledged to have enormous usage by targeted audience (Jiaqi et al., 2021; Krishnaprabha & Tarunika, 2020). Social media tools that are in high use Facebook, Whattssap, Instagram, Twitter, YouTube and LinkedIn (ElAydi, 2018). These tools have transformed the way people communicate and interact over the internet to share information and knowledge (Muma, 2018). Social media is used

by more than 80% teens and young adults in different parts of the world as information and knowledge source (Akudugu et al., 2023). Majhi (2020) asserts that since manufacturers are aware that their customers are an active part of social media, thus they have increased the interest and focus of their marketers to look at social media as a new marketing tool (Jiaqi et al., 2021).

Another prominent digital marketing is content marketing, which is a marketing strategy that creates and shares with targeted customers the relevant articles, images, videos, podcasts, and other media that transmit information of a particular product in order to attract new customers, engage and retain them (Huotari et al., 2015; Vinerean, 2017). The content of those media delivers a message that promotes brand awareness (Holliman & Rowley, 2014). So, if the content is of interest to the customers, then they are expected to vigorously take part and get attached to the brand. This link is expected to create customer brand awareness (Prentice et al., 2019). Ansari et al., (2019) evaluated the impact of content marketing and brand awareness and purchase decisions, and found positive impacts of content marketing on brand awareness and purchases. Similar results were found by Wang et al. (2019), Chen et al. (2021) and Jafarova and Tolon (2022).

Another effective digital marketing type is affiliate marketing in which manufacturer provides a commission to online marketer to promote a product through an advertisement on their web site for visitors (Kannan et al., 2019) and send the company's product information to interested customers (Edwin, 2023; Suresh et al., 2018). Essentially, the affiliate promotes the manufacturer's product by generating online traffic or leads and earns a piece of the profit from each generated sale. These affiliates earn the trust of its visitors, as a result the visitors of these online stores turn to be loyal customers of a brand (Chang et al., 2009). Researches (Abdelhady et al., 2020; Suresh et al., 2018; Ul Haq, 2012) found a positive relationship between affiliate marketing and e-business management toward brand awareness.

In 1990s e-mail marketing was established as a feasible marketing tool due to development of the Internet. Currently, email marketing is considered as a cost-effective marketing tool among digital marketing technologies (Hudák et al., 2017). Thus, various manufacturers use e-mail marketing to market their products or services online. Through email marketing, marketers can foster sustainable relationship with customers through trust and awareness of products features (Ligaraba et al., 2023). E-mail marketing, can be defined as a targeted sending of commercial messages to a list of individuals to make the aware of new products or improved product, discounts, value and other product features (Abdel Baky, 2016) in order to keep them engaged with the product. E-mail marketing, is used to make customers aware of the brand and thus increase site traffic and sales support (Samantaray & Pradhan, 2020). Literatures (Ligaraba et al., 2023; Tubulekas, 2017) have report direct impact of e-mail marketing on brand awareness and loyalty.

Moreover, by using paid advertising as digital marketing tools, is any form of internet advertising that a manufacturer pays for a rented space on an internet platform where they have confirmed that their target audience visit regularly (Ahmed et al., 2019). A study by Okolo et al. (2018) found that paid advertising has positive impact on brand awareness in Enugu, Nigeria. Moreover, a study by Irfan (2019) that was conducted in Gorakhpur India

reported positive and significant relationship between paid advertisement and brand awareness.

Last but not least, pay-per-click is an internet advertising model used to drive traffic to websites, in which a manufacturer pays an online marketer when the ad is clicked (Kapoor et al., 2016). Pay-per-click is one of the most important tools that are used by manufacturers through online marketers to market their company and product to interested customers (Diamantopoulos, 2020). Khraim and Alkrableih (2015) and Mitiku (2021) established direct and statistically significant impact on brand awareness in Jordan and Ethiopia respectively. Therefore, the reviewed literature has shown that social media, content marketing, affiliate marketing, e-mail marketing, paid advertising and pay-per-click are important factors to increase brand awareness. Thus, it is assumed that digital marketing has positive impact on brand awareness. This is the task this study intends to confirm in case of sportswear in Tanzanian context.

Thus, in order to achieve the purpose of this study, it was crucial to develop null hypotheses from the review of prior empirical research regarding digital marketing and its impacts on brand awareness. As a result, about six hypotheses were formulated.

H₁: There is no positive and significant association between social media marketing and brand awareness

H₂: Content marketing has no positive and significant association with brand awareness

H₃: There is no direct and significant link between affiliate marketing and brand awareness

H₄: email marketing has no positive and significant association with brand awareness

H₅: Paid advertising has no positive and significant link with brand awareness

H₆: There is no direct and significant link between pay-per-click marketing and brand awareness

Conceptual Framework

The digital marketing tools increases ability of manufacturer to reach out to the customers which significantly increase brand awareness. By using digital media effectively, the manufacturers can connect with their targeted customers with a greater efficiency. Due to the interactive nature of digital media also the customers can have deeper relationships with the manufacturers. The customers can provide their opinion regarding the way they like products to be. As a consequence of using digital marketing tools the customers can have get a lot of information and knowledge about the brand of their choice.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework for Digital Marketing and Brand Awareness
Source: Muma (2018), Jiaqi et al. (2021), Ariyani and Septiani (2022), Karen and Zai (2022)

Research Methodology

Area of Study and Research Design

This study was carried out in Dar es Salaam City in Tanzania, and particularly in four Wards namely, Mjimwema and Tungi in Kigamboni District, and Kawe and Mwenge in Kinondoni District. The city has been chosen because most of sportswear manufacturers are located there, and also major sports events take place in the city since major sports grounds are located in the region (Leguna & Lucian, 2021; Ndee, 2002; Ungruhe & Schmidt, 2020) and it is the home for major football clubs such as Dar es Salaam Young Africans, Simba Sports Club and Azam FC to mention a few. Based on these, the sportswear market is huge in the region. Moreover, the City is the largest in the country in terms of both population and economic activities. It is the business hub of the country. Consequently, it was expected to have a larger population of sports fun, and hence data could quickly be collected.

Research Design and Approaches

This research was approached using pure quantitative methods, suggesting the application of analytic cross-sectional research design. The reason for choosing analytic design is due to the fact that this study intended to estimate the impact of digital marketing on brand awareness. Analytic studies are designed to measure cause-effect relationship among variables (Provost, 2011; Ranganathan & Aggarwal, 2019). In addition, the use of cross-sectional design in this study was informed by its ability to measure outcome and exposures in the study participants at only one point in time (Setia, 2016; Schmidt & Brown, 2019). The combination of analytic and cross-sectional designs allows for the minimisation of sampling errors and bias and thus enhances the chance for findings obtained from data collected at one point in time from a small sample to be inferred to the whole population (Terrell, 2012), nevertheless, rather so cautiously.

Population and Sampling Methods

Total population of the study comprised of sportswear buyers in Tanzania. However, the sampling frame consisted of sportswear buyers in Dar es Salaam region. The sample size was estimated using scientific reasoning based on the requirement of multiple regression model as stipulated by Montgomery, Peck and Vining (2012), Beaujean (2014) and Cargnelutti & Toebee (2020) that regression models provide robust results if sample size is not less than 200 participants. With the help of Ward Executive Officer (WEO) or Mtaa Executive Officer (MEO), the researcher selected study participants at sports centres and street grounds where locals tend to gather for recreational purposes and for watching sports games. The WEO introduced the researcher to sports fans, and the researcher introduced the study and explained its purpose followed by requesting them to participate in the study at their free will.

Then after accepting to participate in the study, the respondents were selected using purposive and random methods. Firstly, sports fans were purposively selected from among the gathered people by considering their age, education and sex so as to have a representative sample. The common criteria for selection of sports fan was possession of sportswear either wearing at a time or having it at home. This criteria was envisaged to enable the researcher to select people who could inform the study which digital marketing tools influenced him/her to select a particular brand, and hence establish the relationship between digital marketing tool and brand awareness. Then from a group of these sports fans simple random selection was used to select respondents for this study. In total 264 respondents were sampled from different sports centres in the City and given a questionnaire. All distributed questionnaires were returned but only 250 questionnaires were judged usable, and hence utilised for data analysis. This number of questionnaires was considered optimal for regression analysis and enough for inferring findings to the population.

Data Collection

The data was collected using a structured questionnaire with closed-ended questions. The questions were in five-point Likert scale in order to measure the extent digital marketing media have impacted brand awareness among sportswear buyers or sports fans. During data collection the researcher distributed the prepared self-administered questionnaire to the sportswear buyers and collected it in 15-30 minutes after being filled. The questionnaire was designed to be self-explanatory/administered. A request to participate in the study was forwarded to the sportswear buyer by the researcher, and upon agreeing the sportswear buyer was given a questionnaire to fill.

Data Analysis Plan

In the analysis of data this study adopted descriptive statistics and multiple linear regression model. Descriptive statistics mapped the extent of application of digital marketing in Dar es Salaam City. The multiple linear regression model was used to estimate the impact of digital marketing on brand awareness among sportswear customers. A multiple linear regression model was used for the reason that it is a statistical technique that predicts the value of a dependent variable based on the values of two or

more independent variables (Tranmer & Elliot, 2008). To run regression analysis, independent variables measured in five-point Likert scale were entered in the regression model to estimate their link with dependent variable ‘brand awareness’ measured numerically using 1-10 scale of awareness. The scale of 1 being low level of awareness of sports brands and scale of 10 being the highest awareness of sports brand. Also, the five Likert scale was ordered from 1=strongly disagreed to 5=strongly agree. Participants were instructed to show the level of agreeing or disagreeing with the statements that described how a specific digital tool helped him/her to be aware with sportswear brands.

Analytical Model

Multiple linear regression model provided in equation (1) was utilised to estimate the regression coefficients for social media marketing, content marketing, affiliate marketing, e-mail marketing, paid advertising marketing and pay-per-click marketing; on brand awareness.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \beta_5X_5 + \beta_6X_6 + \varepsilon \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where;

Y = Personal savings (percentage change in savings amount)

β_0 = Intercept (Constant)

β_1 = Regression Coefficient of Social media marketing,

β_2 = Regression Coefficient of Content marketing,

β_3 = Regression Coefficient of Affiliate marketing,

β_4 = Regression Coefficient of e-mail marketing

β_5 = Regression Coefficient of Paid advertising marketing

β_6 = Regression Coefficient of Pay-per-Click marketing

X_1 = Social media marketing

X_2 = Content marketing

X_3 = Affiliate marketing

X_4 = e-mail marketing

X_5 = Paid advertising marketing

X_6 = Pay-per-Click marketing

ε = Error term for the model

Econometric tests for regression assumptions

As a procedure, data analytical tests were carried out prior data analysis commences. A range of preliminary tests were performed to check the appropriateness of data for modelling and statistical analyses. Testing of assumptions is essential in case multiple linear regressions model is applied for data analysis. These include; normality, multicollinearity, autocorrelation, heteroskedasticity, linearity and reliability. Serious disobedience of the assumptions results in biased estimates and over or underestimated accuracy of predicted coefficients (lower predictive power). Also, violation of these econometric requirements can cause high standard error and unreliable confidence intervals and significance tests. Rigorous assumptions testing aims at making sure there is good fit of data in the model.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Results

A researcher surveyed 250 sportswear customers in Kigamboni and Kinondoni Districts in Dar es Salaam region. Table 1 show that 72.0% were male and 28.0% were female. The finding is similar to Theis, Lefore, Meinzen-Dick et al. (2018) and Radovic-Markovic, Kabir & Jovicic (2020) who reported that, men than women have higher likelihood of adopting and using new technology. Meanwhile based on their age majority of sportswear customers had 18-30 years of age (51.2%) followed by those with 31-44 years (32.4%). The findings of this study corroborate with Sasmita and Suki (2015), Confos and Davis (2016) and Amin (2018) who found out that most of young and middle-aged people used digital marketing tools to access information regarding degree programs offered by private universities in Jordan. In addition, researchers (Akudugu et al., 2023) have acknowledged that age is among the factors that influence adoption and use of new technologies.

According to the education level, majority of sportswear customers had secondary education (44.4%) followed by those with tertiary education (34.0%). The findings corroborate with Sakala and Phiri (2019) who found that primary education now days has been a foundation for application of ICT in daily life. In case of income level, majority of sportswear customers had low (49.6%) and medium (48.0%) income. Those with high income were at lower end (2.4%). The findings of Ashraf and Mohammed (2012) and Diamantopoulos (2019) corroborate with what this study has established.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents Characteristics (N=250)

Variable/parameter	Measurement	Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Male	180	72.0
	Female	70	28.0
Age	18-30 Years	128	51.2
	31-44 Years	81	32.4
	45+ Years	41	16.4
Education level	Primary	54	21.6
	Secondary	111	44.4
	Tertiary	85	34.0
Income level	Low	124	49.6
	Medium	120	48.0
	High	6	02.4

Furthermore, mean scores of social media marketing (M=4.49, SD=894; range 2-5), paid advertising marketing (M=4.23, SD=1.007; range 1-5) and pay-per-click marketing (M=4.71, SD=.645; range 2-5) indicate that sportswear customers strongly agree that they use these digital marketing tools to search for information of different brands. Besides, content marketing (M=3.89, SD=.908; range 1-5) and affiliate marketing (M=3.98, SD=1.013; range 1-5) have mean score in a scale of agree. These findings signify that sportswear customers had largely agreed that they use digital marketing to enhance their

awareness regarding sportswear brands of their choice. The findings corroborate with Hermawan (2019), Abdelhady et al. (2020), Jafarora and Tolon (2022), Ariyani and Septiani (2022) who found that digital marketing tools are highly used by customers to search for information and knowledge on products they like or want to buy.

However, the results show that sportswear customers disagreed to have received marketing message via their email. This means that most customers have not used e-mail marketing as a way to look for information and knowledge regarding different sportswear brands (M=1.87, SD=.996; range 1-5). The findings are contrary to previous studies of Baky (2016) and Tubulekas (2017) who reported that e-mail marketing has positive and significant effect on brand awareness. However, this study acknowledges the importance of e-mail marketing as an ideal tool for digital marketing. Various manufacturers use e-mail marketing to expose their products to customers. Through email marketing, marketers can foster sustainable relationship with customers through trust and awareness of products features (Ligaraba et al., 2023). It is regarded as a cost-effective marketing tool among digital marketing technologies.

Table 2. Measures of Central Tendency and Dispersion for Digital Marketing (N=250)

Digital marketing	N	Mean	S. D	Min	Max
Social media marketing	250	4.49	.894	2	5
Content marketing	250	3.89	.908	1	5
Affiliate marketing	250	3.93	1.013	1	5
e-mail marketing	250	1.87	.996	1	5
Paid advertising marketing	250	4.23	1.007	1	5
Pay-per-click marketing	250	4.71	.645	2	5

Inferential statistics

Table 3 illustrate that R=0.839 is a very high correlation, and it means that digital marketing reliably predicts brand awareness. The R-Square, has a value of 0.704, indicate that digital marketing media (social media marketing, content marketing, affiliate marketing, e-mail marketing, paid advertising marketing and pay-per-click marketing) influenced 70.4 % of the variability of brand awareness. Thus, 29.6% of the variation is caused by factors other than the predictors included in this model. However, a value of adjusted R-square (0.700) indicates that true 70.0% of variation in brand awareness was explained by social media marketing, content marketing, affiliate marketing, e-mail marketing, paid advertising marketing and pay-per-click marketing. The discrepancy between R-squared and Adjusted R Square (=0.004) signify that the model fits well to the data. Since, Adjusted R Square is greater than 33%, the effect of predictors of digital marketing on brand awareness is strong as stipulated by Ghazali & Latan (2015).

Table 3: Model Summary for Digital Marketing (N=250)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.839 ^a	.704	.700	.37550

Predictors: (Constant), social media marketing, content marketing, affiliate marketing, e-mail marketing, paid advertising marketing, pay-per-click marketing

The F-ratio in the ANOVA, tests whether the overall regression model is a good fit for the data. The results in Table 4 show that the independent variables statistically significantly predict the dependent variable, $F(3, 373) = 1841.960, p(.000)$. In other words, the regression model is a good fit to the data. Table 5 demonstrates that VIF for all predictor variables was <10 and Tolerance >0.1 , which means there was no multicollinearity in the estimated regression model. Also, results specify that brand awareness would be 4.316 when all predictor variables were zero.

Table 4. ANOVA^a for Digital Marketing (N=250)

	Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	779.149	3	259.716	1841.960	.000 ^b
	Residual	52.485	373	0.141		
	Total	831.634	376			

a. Dependent Variable: Brand awareness

b. Predictors: (Constant), social media marketing, content marketing, affiliate marketing, e-mail marketing, paid advertising marketing, pay-per-click marketing

Furthermore, in this study, hypothesis testing was conducted to confirm impact of digital marketing on brand awareness among sportswear customers in Dar es Salaam City. The test statistic used was 5% level of significance, whereby the value less than 5% or 0.005 indicated the significant impact between the digital marketing and brand awareness. Otherwise, the result was not statistically significant. The results in Table 5 shows estimation of the impact of social media marketing on brand awareness was ($\beta=5.983, t=59.239, p(.000) < 0.05$). Therefore, this study rejected the hypothesis ***H₁: There is no positive and significant association between social media marketing and brand awareness.*** These results conclude that the social media marketing had a significant positive impact on brand awareness. The better the quality of the social media marketing strategies of sportswear manufacturers through the application of social media marketing, the more significant it can be in increasing brand awareness of sportswear customers in Dar es Salaam City.

Karen and Zai (2022) posit that social media networks are part of manufacturer and customer interaction in the web market. With social media marketing tools, it is easier for manufacturers to enhance brand awareness in less time and with low costs to a lot of targeted individuals than traditional marketing strategies that are typically extra expensive (Mitiku, 2021). Using social media platforms, consumers can instantly connect with new products, services and brands easily (Febriyanto, 2020). Amin (2018) posit that manufacturers must design digital marketing platforms that have the ability to provide information and knowledge about products to customers. As such, digital marketing platforms with vague and ambiguous message and view could de-motivate and discourage sharing of the information and knowledge regarding the product on display or pass negative comments regarding the product (Hermawan, 2019; Ariyani & Septiani, 2022).

The findings of the impact of content marketing on brand awareness was positive and statistically significant ($\beta=4.236, t=9.540, p(.000) < 0.05$). This finding concludes that as content marketing campaign of sportswear manufacturers increases its impact on brand

awareness among sportswear customers increase too. Accordingly, ***H₂: Content marketing has no positive and significant association with brand awareness*** was rejected. Thus, the better content marketing strategies by sportswear manufacturers, the brand awareness of sportswear customers in Dar es Salaam City will also be better. Similar to the findings of this study Ansari et al., (2019), Chen et al. (2021) and Jafarova and Tolon (2022) found positive impacts of content marketing on brand awareness.

Content marketing is a digital marketing strategy that uses digital tools such as text, images, and video to create value and engagement to customers. The contained message must be true and authentic in order to catch customer's trust and commitment, which in turn build brand loyalty. Thus, as the content information talk about the brand and its benefits, then this content is expected to assist customers in creating brand awareness and building a successful relationship among the brand and customers (Vinerean, 2017; Chen et al., 2021). True content marketing delivers value and trust to customers. The good content marketing message must follow the principle of 5Cs. The principle says that every good piece of content must be clear, concise, compelling, credible, and calls to action.

The result of the impact of affiliate marketing on brand awareness of sportswear customers in Dar es Salaam City was ($\beta=2.907$, $t=8.442$, $p (.001) < 0.05$). This finding concludes that brand awareness had a statistically significant positive impact on brand awareness. The third hypothesis ***H₃: There is no direct and significant link between affiliate marketing and brand awareness*** was rejected. Therefore, better affiliate marketing guarantee better brand awareness of sportswear customers. Abdelhady, Kamal & Samie (2020) argued that affiliate marketing has been a popular tool used by customers to gather product information and create brand awareness. Similarly, Haq (2012) and Suresh et al. (2018) found positive impact of affiliate marketing on brand awareness.

Affiliate marketing supports the visitors to easily search for information of a product(s) by publishing in their popular websites or blogs or social media pages. These platforms support in attracting website traffic and connect manufacturers and producers with audiences to increase brand awareness, and hence sales (Kannan et al., 2019; Kakoti & Rroy, 2023). The usage of affiliate marketing activities supports in increasing brand awareness as it supports in attracting inbound traffic and thus effectively advertise the products. Affiliate marketing is used as a tool to attract the interest and provide an incentive for customers to take a desired action toward a specified manufacturer (Nwogu, 2019). According to Benediktova and Nevosad (2008) and Bystrova (2015), affiliate marketing usually is designed to accomplish a specific purpose such as assisting a manufacturer to launch a new business or attract customers and lure them away from a competitor.

Table 5. Regression Results for Digital Marketing (n=377)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	4.316	.512		8.430	.000		
1 Social media marketing	5.983	.101	.480	59.239	.000	.905	1.204
Content marketing	4.236	.444	.233	9.540	.000	.488	2.408
Affiliate marketing	2.907	.344	.369	8.442	.001	.500	2.053
e-mail marketing	.192	.233	.071	.823	.509	.419	2.411
Paid advertising marketing	8.793	.476	.529	18.473	.000	.858	3.836
Pay-per-click marketing	16.465	.482	.672	34.159	.000	.451	2.737

Dependent Variable: Brand awareness

In case of paid advertising marketing, the result shows impact of paid advertising marketing on brand awareness among sportswear customers in Dar es Salaam City was ($\beta=8.793$, $t=18.473$, $p(0.001) < 0.05$). This finding concludes that paid advertising marketing had a statistically significant positive impact on brand awareness. Thus, the fifth hypothesis ***H₅: Paid advertising has no positive and significant link with brand awareness*** was rejected. Therefore, better paid advertising marketing warrants brand awareness of sportswear customers. The findings corroborate with Okolo et al. (2018) and Irfan (2019) who also found significant positive impact of paid advertising marketing on brand awareness in Nigeria and India respectively.

Brand awareness can be increased through paid advertising tools that inform, remind, and convince customers about the products of their choice. Diamantopoulos (2019) asserts that digital advertising campaigns are necessary for any brand that is aimed to reach the targeted customer online and increase their conversion rate through the marketing channel. The paid advertising cost very low compared to the traditional print and electronic media (Okolo et al., 2018). Paid advertisement is a valuable and resourceful method for advertisers to conveniently design an ad message to target the specific current and potential customers of a products. Through paid advertising manufacturers are able to reach their different audience with targeted ad messages (Domazet et al., 2017). As a result, this media has great accuracy and saves time and money (Lou & Koh, 2018).

Regarding pay-per-click marketing, findings revealed that positive and statistically significant ($\beta=16.465$, $t=34.159$, $p(.000) < 0.05$) impact on brand awareness. This means that every unit increase in pay-per-click marketing activities by sportswear manufacturers, increases awareness of their brands by 4.236. In general, the hypotheses ***H₆: There is no direct and significant link between pay-per-click marketing and brand awareness*** was rejected. The results suggest that pay-per-click marketing as one of digital marketing tool is a very crucial determinant of brand awareness in sportswear industry. Prior research conducted by Imashava (2019) and Mitiku (2021) reported significant positive effect of pay-per-click marketing on brand awareness.

On the contrary, the findings in Table 5 illustrates a positive but statistically not significant impact on brand awareness ($\beta=.192$, $t= .823$, $p (.509)>0.05$). Therefore, hypothesis ***H₄: email marketing has no positive and significant association with brand awareness*** was accepted. This means that the ability of e-mail marketing does not add a meaningful explanation regarding brand awareness. This is because there is no substantial evidence to confirm if the relationship between e-mail marketing and brand awareness exists. Though we lack evidence to show connection between e-mail marketing and brand awareness, literature has acknowledged that e-mail marketing has positive impact on brand awareness among consumers (Hudak et al., 2017; Samantaray & Pradhan, 2020; Ligaraba et al., 2023).

Despite the inconclusive result, the importance of e-mail marketing as the cheapest tool for digital marketing is acknowledged in marketing management practices and research. Manufacturers and suppliers alike frequently use e-mail marketing to communicate with their customers regarding their products. Thus, the application of email marketing enables marketers to encourage long term relationship with customers through raising their product awareness. The finding of this study should be taken into consideration with caution by the marketers as there is a possibility that the opinions given by the sports fans is inconclusive may be due to either they are not much aware about email marketing or else they are facing some difficulty in using these tools.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Conclusion

The impact of digital marketing on the brand awareness has been appropriately understood in this research for sportswear manufactures. This study focused on content marketing, social media marketing, affiliate marketing, e-mail marketing, paid advertising and pay-per-click marketing tools because are the most used by companies in Tanzania to communicate with customers. The findings of this study show that pay-per-click marketing, paid advertising, social media, content marketing and affiliate marketing are highly applied by sportswear manufacturers for marketing the sportswear. Empirically, these digital marketing tools have positive influence on sportswear brand awareness among sports fans. However, application of e-mail marketing tools was found to be very low and hence its impact on sportswear brand awareness is unknown in the study area.

Thus, this research concludes that the sportswear manufactures are expected to do better in the market when they use the marketing tools to manage both user generated content and firm generated content to engage the maximum number of customers with the business and gain a desired outcome from the business functions. Thus, manufacturers will be able to increase the brand awareness in the mind of their customers. Brand awareness is created through digital marketing through the internet. Effective digital marketing includes not only advertisements on websites, but also social networking, creation of contents or contracting a third part through affiliate contract. The digital marketing tools increases ability of manufacturer to reach out to the customers which significantly increase brand awareness. By using digital media effectively, the manufacturers can connect with their targeted customers with a greater efficiency. Due to the interactive nature of digital media also the customers can have deeper relationships

with the manufacturers. The customers can provide their opinion regarding the way they like products to be. As a consequence of using digital marketing tools the customers can have get a lot of information and knowledge about the brand of their choice. Digital is an innovative way to increase brand awareness.

Theoretical and Practical implications

Theoretical implications

This study has contributed and substantiated the literature of digital marketing research, in the context of creating brand awareness for sportswear customers. Based on the findings this study has confirmed that digital marketing tools actually influences brand awareness of customers through effective exposure compared to traditional advertising methods. Specifically, the study has substantiated the theoretical foundation of stimulus-organism-response theory that when social media marketing, content marketing, affiliate marketing, paid advertising marketing and pay-per-click marketing are used to post and stream different content and messages (stimulus) to customers (organism) they assist in knowledge development and hence increase their awareness of products (response). Thus, it has been confirmed that usage of free advertisement based on pages in online platforms like Facebook and Instagram are influential in engaging customers and keep them aware of brand products online at any time. However, this study shade light to sportswear manufacturers to consider with most care the use of e-mail marketing to raise customers' awareness of their products since its role in this endeavour is not clear in Tanzanian sportswear industry.

Practical implications

This study has developed better contributions for existing and potential sportswear customers that they have to highly focus on digital marketing media platforms for effective information regarding the brand. The implications of this study include to shed light on the importance of digital marketing for rural people who lack necessary infrastructures such as electricity, and thus hinders them from accessing television-based advertising campaigns and other traditional adverts. With sophisticated development of solar power rural people have chance to operate electronic devices such as mobile phones and portable computers to search for information of products of their choice, and hence increase their awareness of those products. Thus, this study attracts rural to use the digital marketing media and other online tools. Also, sportswear manufacturers are provided with strategies they can use to involve or target rural people more effectively. Moreover, this study has shown that digital marketing can enhance positive perception of the sportswear customers and can be used by manufacturers to understand the increase of brand awareness of their products. Furthermore, this study has informed customers that searching for information regarding sportswear products it is less time consuming and low cost as it has a variety of paid advertisements where you can freely search for information. Moreover, based on our findings, it shows that the sportswear manufacturers have to use more paid advertisements marketing since they capture more customers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study the following recommendations were provided. Firstly, sportswear manufacturers should utilize the firm's generated content in order to stimulate the user generated content so that it can achieve the short-term and long-term objectives. Secondly, sportswear manufacturers are advised to consider the of e-mail marketing with caution since its role in increasing brand awareness is not clear among sportswear customers in Tanzania. Thirdly, it is recommended to sportswear to invest heavy and continue to improve their paid advertising and pay-per-click marketing campaigns so that the opinions experiences and information about their brand can be expressed and accessed by the customers. Fourthly, it is also important for sportswear manufactures to effectively monitor the affiliates since they are outside the control of the company's management to make sure what the affiliate follow contract. Lastly but not least, recommendation is also provided to sportswear manufactures to combine digital marketing and traditional marketing strategies for effective ad wide coverage in order to achieve higher brand awareness. The two-marketing media can create a synergy that is more beneficial than using either medium separately.

Limitations and Suggestion for Future Studies

This study has many aspects that required to be investigated in the future researches in the field of digital marketing and brand awareness. One of the limitations in scope of this study is that it focused on study business-to-customer perspective. Thus, future studies should consider investigating how digital marketing affects the relationship of business-to-business as well. Moreover, this study addressed the issue of digital marketing and its impact on brand awareness. The future study could be expanded to focus on the effect of digital marketing on firm performance when moderated by brand awareness. Moreover, this study covered a small geographical area (only Dar es Salaam City). As a result, there a need for future research to cover larger geographical area instead of only one City, the future study should cover more Cities. This is envisaged to provide a better representation of the whole Tanzania population. Also, this study is pure quantitative under the positivist philosophy. Thus, is robbed off the ability to explain concepts in detail. to obtain robust results. It is therefore recommended for a further study to be conducted using both qualitative and quantitative approaches of research. It is expected that if the customers, distributors and manufacturers were included in the unstructured or semi-structured in-depth interviews and focus group discussions it will help to clear out any doubt and have a better perception about brand awareness and how digital marketing tools actually plays their role. Besides, combination of qualitative and quantitative methods is also expected to increase the value in the empirical findings, and gain reliable and detailed explanations.

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References

- Abdel Baky, S. (2016). Email Marketing between Effectiveness and Inconvenience: A Case of Travel Agencies in Cairo. *Journal of Association of Arab Universities for Tourism and Hospitality*, 13(1), 75–84.
<https://doi.org/10.21608/jaauth.2016.49964>
- Abdelhady, M. H., Kamal, N. M., & Abd El Samie, H. (2020). Impact of affiliate marketing on customer loyalty. *Journal of the Faculty of Tourism and Hotels- University of Sadat City*, 4(1/1), 50–71.
- Ahmed, R. R., Streimikiene, D., Berchtold, G., Vveinhardt, J., Channar, Z. A., & Soomro, R. H. (2019). Effectiveness of Online Digital Media Advertising as A Strategic Tool for Building Brand Sustainability: Evidence from FMCGs and Services Sectors of Pakistan. *Sustainability*, 11(12), 3436.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su11123436>
- Akudugu, M. A., Nkegbe, P. K., Wongnaa, C. A., & Millar, K. K. (2023). Technology adoption behaviors of farmers during crises: What are the key factors to consider? *Journal of Agriculture and Food Research*, 14, 100694.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jafr.2023.100694>
- Ariel, Y., & Avidar, R. (2015). Information, Interactivity, and Social Media. *Atlantic Journal of Communication*, 23(1), 19–30.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15456870.2015.972404>
- Bruhn, M., Schoenmueller, V., & Schäfer, D. B. (2012). Are social media replacing traditional media in terms of brand equity creation? *Management Research Review*, 35(9), 770–790. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01409171211255948>
- Chang, H. H., Wang, Y.-H., & Yang, W.-Y. (2009). The impact of e-service quality, customer satisfaction and loyalty on e-marketing: Moderating effect of perceived value. *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*, 20(4), 423–443.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14783360902781923>
- Chen, X., Shen, X., Huang, X., & Li, Y. (2021). Research on social media content marketing: An empirical analysis based on China's 10 metropolis for Korean brands. *SAGE Open*, 11(4), 21582440211052951.
- Diamantopoulos, F.-N. (2020). The impact of digital advertising on the marketing of consumers' products for Kotsovolos company.
- Edwin, W. S. (2023). The Influence of Digital Marketing on Purchase Intention with Brand Awareness as a Mediating Variable. *International Journal of Review Management Business and Entrepreneurship (RMBE)*, 3(1), 21–29.
<https://doi.org/10.37715/rmbe.v3i1.3929>

- ElAydi, H. O. (2018). The Effect of Social Media Marketing on Brand Awareness through Facebook: An Individual-Based Perspective of Mobile Services Sector in Egypt. *OALib*, 05(10), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1104977>
- Ghozali, I., & Latan, H. (2015). Partial least squares konsep, teknik dan aplikasi menggunakan program smartpls 3.0 untuk penelitian empiris. Semarang: Badan Penerbit UNDIP, 4(1).
- Hakala, U., Svensson, J., & Vincze, Z. (2012). Consumer-based brand equity and top-of-mind awareness: A cross-country analysis. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 21(6), 439–451. <https://doi.org/10.1108/10610421211264928>
- Halik, J., Halik, M., Nurlia, N., Hardiyono, H., & Alimuddin, I. (2021). The Effect of Digital Marketing and Brand Awareness on the Performance of SMEs in Makassar City. *Proceedings of the First International Conference on Economics, Business and Social Humanities, ICONEBS 2020*, November 4-5, 2020, Madiun, Indonesia. <https://doi.org/10.4108/eai.4-11-2020.2304613>
- Han, M. S., Hampson, D. P., Wang, Y., & Wang, H. (2022). Consumer confidence and green purchase intention: An application of the stimulus-organism-response model. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 68, 103061. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2022.103061>
- Hetharie, J. A., Hussein, A. S., & Puspaningrum, A. (2019). SOR (Stimulus-organism-response) model application in observing the influence of impulsive buying on consumer's post-purchase regret. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 8(11), 2829–2841.
- Holliman, G., & Rowley, J. (2014). Business to business digital content marketing: Marketers' perceptions of best practice. *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*, 8(4), 269–293. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JRIM-02-2014-0013>
- Hudák, M., Kianičková, E., & Madleňák, R. (2017). The Importance of E-mail Marketing in E-commerce. *Procedia Engineering*, 192, 342–347. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2017.06.059>
- Huotari, L., Ulkuniemi, P., Saraniemi, S., & Mäläskä, M. (2015). Analysis of content creation in social media by B2B companies. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 30(6), 761–770. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JBIM-05-2013-0118>
- Ioanăș, E., & Stoica, I. (2014). Social media and its impact on consumers behavior. *International Journal of Economic Practices and Theories*, 4(2), 295–303.
- Jafarova, K., & Tolon, M. (2022). The Effect of Content Marketing in Social Media on Brand Loyalty and Purchase Intention. *Journal of Business Management and Economic Research*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.29226/TR1001.2022.318>
- Jayadi, J., Putra, E. I., & Murwani, I. A. (2022). The Implementation of S-O-R Framework (Stimulus, Organism, and Response) in User Behavior Analysis of

- Instagram Shop Features on Purchase Intention. *Scholars Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 10(4), 42–53. <https://doi.org/10.36347/sjet.2022.v10i04.003>
- Jiaqi, Y., Teo, B. S.-X., Tingting, L., & Jiaxun, Z. (2021). Influence of social media marketing in building relationship between brand loyalty of tourism products and products service quality. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 251, 03006. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202125103006>
- Kamadi, Y., Aras, M., Andriani, N., & Bayani, H. D. (2022). Enhancing brand awareness through digital communication strategies. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, 100(23).
- Kannan, A. S., Raj, M. A., & Priyanka, M. S. (2019). A Study on Awareness of Affiliate Marketing among MBA students in Puducherry.
- Kapoor, K. K., Dwivedi, Y. K., & Piercy, N. C. (2016). Pay-per-click advertising: A literature review. *The Marketing Review*, 16(2), 183–202. <https://doi.org/10.1362/146934716X14636478977557>
- Krishnaprabha, S., & Tarunika, R. (2020). An analysis on building brand awareness through digital marketing initiatives. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management*, 3(7), 266–270.
- Leguna, P. G., & Lucian, C. (2021). Facilities Management of Sports Infrastructure in Tanzania: A Case Study of the Stadia in Dar Es Salaam. *The 20th Annual Afres Conference*, 19.
- Ligaraba, N., Chuchu, T., & Nyagadza, B. (2023). Opt-in e-mail marketing influence on consumer behaviour: A Stimuli–Organism–Response (S–O–R) theory perspective. *Cogent Business & Management*, 10(1), 2184244. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2023.2184244>
- Mehrabian, A., & Russell, J. A. (1974). *An approach to environmental psychology*. the MIT Press.
- Mitiku, A. (2021). The impact of digital marketing on brand awareness and brand loyalty: The case of Awash Wine SC. ST. MARY’S UNIVERSITY.
- Muma, H. P. (2018). *The Influence of Social Media Marketing on Brand Awareness: A Survey on Consumers of Soft Drink Beverages in Kisumu City, Kenya*. university of nairobi.
- Ndee, H. S. (2002). Modern Sport in Independent Tanzania: “Adapted” Sport and the Process of Modernization. *The International Journal of the History of Sport*, 19(4), 89–113. <https://doi.org/10.1080/714001797>
- Prentice, C., Han, X. Y., Hua, L.-L., & Hu, L. (2019). The influence of identity-driven customer engagement on purchase intention. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 47, 339–347. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2018.12.014>

- Provost L. P. (2011). Analytical studies: a framework for quality improvement design and analysis. *BMJ quality & safety*, 20 Suppl 1(Suppl_1), i92–i96. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjqs.2011.051557>
- Ranganathan, P. & Aggarwal, R. (2019). Study designs: Part 3: Analytical observational studies. *Perspectives in clinical research*, 10(2), 91–94. https://doi.org/10.4103/picr.PICR_35_19
- Saif, T., Ahmed, M., Shareef, S., & Khalid, R. (2018). Characteristics of brand loyalty: A study on apparel industry. *Mediterranean Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences (MJBAS)*, 2(2), 64–69.
- Samantaray, A., & Pradhan, B. B. (2020). Importance of e-mail marketing. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 17(6), 5219–5227.
- Schmidt N. A. & Brown J. M. (2019). *Evidence-based practice for nurses: Appraisal and application of research* (4th ed.). Jones & Bartlett Learning
- Segson, U., & Tan, C. C. (2018). Application of Stimulus-organism-response (Sor) theory to study consumer behavior of upscale restaurants in Northern Thailand. *ASEAN/Asian Academic Society International Conference Proceeding Series*, 701–708.
- Setia M. S. (2016). Methodology Series Module 3: Cross-sectional Studies. *Indian journal of dermatology*, 61(3), 261–264. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0019-5154.182410>
- Sharma, S., Singh, S., Kujur, F., & Das, G. (2020). Social Media Activities and Its Influence on Customer-Brand Relationship: An Empirical Study of Apparel Retailers' Activity in India. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 16(4), 602–617. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jtaer16040036>
- Siby, B. (2021). A Study on The Factors Influencing Consumer Response and Brand Value as A Result of Digital Marketing in Standalone Restaurant. June.
- Sukrat, S. (2018). A MATURITY MODEL FOR C2C SOCIAL COMMERCE BUSINESS MODEL. *International Journal of Electronic Commerce Studies*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.7903/ijecs.1545>
- Suresh, V., Maran, K., & AR, S. P. (2018). A Study On Impact Of An Affiliate Marketing In E-Business For Consumer's Perspective. *International Journal of Engineering and Technology (IJET)*, 10(2), 470–473.
- Tenzin Choedon, & Lee, Young-Chan. (2020). The Effect of Social Media Marketing Activities on Purchase Intention with Brand Equity and Social Brand Engagement: Empirical Evidence from Korean Cosmetic Firms. *Knowledge Management Review*, 21(3), 141–160. <https://doi.org/10.15813/KMR.2020.21.3.008>

- Terrell, S. R. (2012). Mixed-methods research methodologies. *Qualitative Report*, 17(1), 254–280.
- Tranmer, M., & Elliot, M. (2008). Multiple linear regression. *The Cathie Marsh Centre for Census and Survey Research (CCSR)*, 5(5), 1–5.
- Tubulekas, A. (2017). The effects of personalized email communication within loyalty programs for businesses without possibilities for e-commerce.
- Ul Haq, Z. (2012). Affiliate marketing programs: A study of consumer attitude towards affiliate marketing programs among Indian users. *International Journal of Research Studies in Management*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrsm.2012.v1i1.84>
- Ungruhe, C., & Schmidt, M. B. (2020). Why are East African Players Absent in European Football? Localizing African Football Migration Along Structural Constraints, Colonial Legacies and Voluntary Immobility. *Journal of Sport and Social Issues*, 44(5), 397–420. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0193723520919820>
- Vinerean, S. (2017). Content marketing strategy: Definition, objectives and tactics. *Expert Journal of Marketing*, 5(2), 92–98.
- Voramontri, D., & Klieb, L. (2019). Impact of social media on consumer behaviour. *International Journal of Information and Decision Sciences*, 11(3), 209. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJIDS.2019.101994>
- Wu, Y.-L., & Li, E. Y. (2018). Marketing mix, customer value, and customer loyalty in social commerce: A stimulus-organism-response perspective. *Internet Research*, 28(1), 74–104. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IntR-08-2016-0250>

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